

Mapping Research Topics on Islamic Pawnshop: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the development of research around Islamic Pawnshop. The research was conducted from 1999 to 2022, by searching national journals indexed by Sinta via the Garuda website, with the keyword "Islamic Pawnshop". Based on the search results, there were 312 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a literature review study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to Islamic Pawnshop is divided into 4 clusters and 115 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a literature review study, there are 8 main themes related to Islamic Pawnshop.

Keywords: Islamic Pawnshop, Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review

Introduction

PT Pegadaian (Persero)'s alternative facilities, which are well known to the wider public, have recently begun to emerge and develop a new image through various media, with the new tagline "Solving Problems Without Problems". This company is a limited company that uses mortgage law to channel its funds. This pawnshop has unique characteristics, namely providing services to the public while generating profits using business management principles.

Islamic Pawnshop are financial institutions that follow sharia laws in general. Currently, Islamic Pawnshop are developing in forms of collateral that are not covered by pawn law, such as fiduciary guarantees. The wide area covered by the administration of second-hand goods stores makes these second-hand goods stores produce sharia-based goods that are advertised through sharia goods shops in order to capture advertising opportunities that cannot be reached by the general public who adhere to Islamic standards and have the principle of carrying out monetary exchanges with a system that follows sharia regulations. Apart from that, Pawnshop owned by the government have not been given a syndication office to operate Islamic Pawnshop in Indonesia. This pawnshop was incorporated as a legal entity before becoming a public company in 1990. The pawnshop service changed its name to Perusahaan Negara (PN) Pegadaian in 1960. In 1990, this pawnshop was published on April 10 1990. The pawnshop's social mission is the only reference used by the management in managing the pawnshop when it was still an office.

Scientific publications about Islamic Pawnshop continue to increase, according to the Garuda Digital Reference (Garuda) website, there are 310 journals that discuss Islamic Pawnshop from 1999 to 2022. The aim of this research is to find out a map of the development of research around Islamic Pawnshop using the method VOSviewer bibliometric and literature review over 23 years.

Literature Review

Islamic Pawnshop are financial institutions that provide credit services based on sharia pawning principles or Islamic law, especially by prioritizing piety, honesty, loyalty, work responsibility, responsiveness, timeliness, and thoroughness as well as politeness, friendliness, empathy in serving customers.

Bibliometric research is the application of statistical and mathematical methods to analyze article and journal publications. Bibliometric research aims to examine and analyze maps of the development of scientific literature. These studies could use more sophisticated multifaceted techniques to analyze simple productivity measures based on article citations. This study is also able to recognize and describe new scientific and technological developments.

VOSviewer is a software that can be developed to build and display bibliometric maps. This program provides text-mining features that can be used to build and project correlation networks in citing an article or publication. VOSviewer can also present and explain specific information about bibliometric graphic maps. Using VOSviewer, we can easily display large bibliometric maps to interpret a correlation.

Literature review e- review is the process of searching and researching books, journals and publications related to a research topic, to obtain writings related to a particular topic or issue. There are two main objectives of a literature review, namely: (1) writing a paper to introduce new studies on a particular topic that people involved in that field of science need to know; and (2) for the benefit of the research project itself. Therefore, making a literature review is very important to deepen our insight into our research topic and help us in formulating research problems.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The object of the research is Islamic Pawnshop. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Islamic Pawnshop originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then searching for journal titles based on the title words category with the keywords " Islamic Pawnshop" and "Islamic Pawnshop" for the entire year period (1999-2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on literature review studies.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Islamic

Pawnshop in Sharia Financial Institutions

The results of a search for scientific research publications regarding Islamic Pawnshop from 1999 to 2022 show that the number reached 312 research articles on this topic. This search was carried out based on accredited national journals. The most publications were achieved in 2021, namely 59 research publications. The average publication per year is 2 published articles.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Islamic Pawnshop

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
1999	1	2013	10	2018	37
2009	4	2014	12	2019	40
2010	2	2015	18	2020	48
2011	1	2016	22	2021	59
2012	2	2017	20	2022	36
Total = 312/Average = 20					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 2 shows that there are 9 affiliates/institutions that publish the most research articles about Islamic Pawnshop. The Journal of Islamic Economics and Business is the largest publishing institution that publishes research results regarding Islamic Pawnshop, reaching 27 articles.

Table 1. Publisher of scientific publications about Islamic Pawnshop

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Journal of Islamic Economics and Business	27
At-Taradhi Journal of Economic Studies	13
ADLIYA: Journal of Law and Humanity	4
Accountthink	3

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Researchers who often write about Islamic Pawnshop are Bambang Irawan, Mulyono, Alfiqoh and Anis.

Bibliometric Mapping Research Regarding Financial Reports in Sharia Financial Institutions

Article search results on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) are exported to RIS (Research Information System) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps regarding Islamic Pawnshop

At Islamic Pawnshop, the fees charged are rental or ujarah fees, while at conventional Pawnshop the fees charged are interest. (3) In Islamic Pawnshop, gold ownership remains with the customer, whereas in conventional Pawnshop, gold ownership becomes the property of the pawnshop after maturity and the customer cannot take the gold back. (4) In Islamic Pawnshop, the contract used is a sale and purchase agreement (murabahah) or rental contract (ijarah), while in conventional Pawnshop, the contract used is a pawn contract. (5) Islamic Pawnshop use transparent and fair gold valuation, which is based on the current market price of gold, whereas in conventional Pawnshop, the gold valuation may be lower than the current market price of gold. (6) At Islamic Pawnshop, funds received from customers are used for financing that is in accordance with sharia principles, while at conventional Pawnshop, funds received can be used for financing that may not be in accordance with sharia principles.

Second, a comparison of the law on determining the ujarah of gold pawning in Islamic Pawnshop and sharia banking, namely:

- Ujarah Calculation Method. In Pegadaian Syariah, the determination of the gold pledge is done using the Musyarakah Mutanaqisah method. This method refers to the principle of revenue sharing between the owner of the goods and the owner of the capital invested in the transaction. Meanwhile, in Syariah banking, the determination of the gold pledge is usually done using the Murabahah method, which is the repurchase of goods at a price higher than the initial purchase price plus an agreed profit.
- The amount of Ujarah. The ujarah amount set at Sharia Pegadaian tends to be lower than in Sharia banking. This is because at Pegadaian Syariah, the risk management system is easier to implement, so there is no need to add significant costs. Meanwhile, in Sharia banking, the ujarah amount is usually higher because the risks that must be borne are greater.
- Security. Even though both financial institutions have security mechanisms, Islamic Pawnshop have the advantage because the goods being pledged, namely gold, are stored in very safe pawnshop vaults. Meanwhile, in Sharia banking, collateralized goods may be stored elsewhere or stored in the bank with different levels of security.
- Terms and Conditions. The terms and conditions for applying for a gold pawn at Sharia Pegadaian and Sharia banking can also be different. However, basically, both financial institutions require the same documents, namely valid personal identity, a certificate or proof of gold ownership, and information about the goods being pledged as collateral.

Third, the accounting treatment for Rahn financing for gold pawning is based on PSAK 107. According to PSAK 107 Sharia Financing Accounting, Rahn financing for gold pawning must be carried out in the following stages: (1) Gold Appraisal, that is, it is necessary to assess the gold that will be pawned. This appraisal is carried out by an independent appraiser who has expertise in appraising gold. This assessment is carried out to determine the market value of the gold. (2) Delivery of Gold. After the market value of the gold has been determined, the customer then hands over the gold to the Islamic bank as a form of collateral for Rahn's financing. (3) Providing Financing. After the gold is received by the Islamic bank, the bank then provides Rahn financing to the customer in an amount equivalent to the market value of the mortgaged gold. (4) Gold Custody. The gold that has been pawned is then entrusted to a sharia

bank as a form of collateral for the financing provided. (5) Gold Recovery. After the customer has paid off Rahn's financing, the gold that has been pawned can be redeemed by the customer according to the predetermined market value.

Fourth, Murabahah and Rahn contracts on eternal gold/precious metal products. In the context of eternal gold or precious metal products at the Sharia Pegadaian, the Murabahah contract is carried out with the following steps: (1) The prospective buyer comes to the Syariah Pegadaian and chooses the eternal gold or precious metal product he wants to buy; (2) Pegadaian Syariah provides information to prospective buyers about the basic price of the product, storage costs, administration costs, etc. incurred by Pegadaian Syariah for the product; (3) After the prospective buyer agrees to the basic price, Pegadaian Syariah adds a fixed profit or margin in accordance with the agreement to obtain the selling price informed to the prospective buyer; (4) Prospective buyers make payments according to the agreed selling price; and (5) After payment is received, Pegadaian Syariah issues a certificate of ownership of the eternal gold or precious metal product that has been purchased by the prospective buyer.

Fifth, operational gold investment products. Gold investment products at Sharia Pegadaian can be done through the Sharia Gold Savings (TES) and Sharia Gold Pawn (GES) programs. Sharia Gold Savings (TES), which is a sharia-based gold investment program managed by Pegadaian Syariah. You can buy gold from 0.01 gram to 1 kilogram. Sharia Gold Pawn (GES), a sharia-based gold pawn program managed by Pegadaian Syariah. These two gold investment programs at Pegadaian Syariah comply with sharia principles so that gold investment is guaranteed to be halal. Apart from that, Sharia Pegadaian also provides guarantees for the security and storage of gold.

Sixth, accounting for gold savings. In sharia accounting, gold savings will be recorded as part of the "Amanah" or "Trust Fund" account because the pawnshop acts as a trustee for the gold held by the customer. The process of recording transactions in gold savings accounting at Islamic Pawnshop can be explained as follows: (1) Every time a customer makes a gold deposit, the pawnshop will record the amount of gold received in the "Amanah" or "Trust Fund" account and issue a gold certificate as proof of ownership; (2) When the customer wants to take back the gold they have deposited, the pawnshop will record the amount of gold taken in the "Amanah" or "Trust Fund" account and cancel the gold certificate; (3) Pegadaian will also record all administrative and service costs related to gold savings in the "Revenue" account; (4) In the case of profits obtained from gold investments, the pawnshop will record them in the "Profit" or "Profit" account. For customers, the benefits received are in the form of additional grams of gold in their savings balance.

Seventh, implementation of gold savings buyback. Implementing a gold savings buyback at Pegadaian Syariah can be carried out using the following steps: (1) The customer comes to the Pegadaian Syariah office with a gold certificate that he wants to resell; (2) Islamic Pawnshop employees will check the completeness of the gold certificate documents brought by the customer; (3) After the completeness of the documents has been checked and declared complete, the Sharia Pegadaian employee will offer a buyback price for the gold in accordance with the market price prevailing at that time; (4) If the customer agrees with the price offered, Pegadaian Syariah will make payment to the customer according to the value of the gold sold; (5) Next, Pegadaian Syariah will take the customer's gold certificate as proof of repurchase of the gold.

Eighth, risk management of gold pawning. Gold pawning risk management at Pegadaian Syariah involves steps to identify, measure and

manage risks associated with gold pawning activities. Several steps that can be taken are as follows: (1) Risk identification: First of all, Sharia Pegadaian must identify the risks associated with gold pawning activities. Some risks that may be associated with gold pawning activities are credit risk, liquidity risk, market risk, operational risk, compliance risk and reputation risk. (2) Measure risk: Once the risk is identified, Pegadaian Syariah needs to measure the risk using appropriate risk measurement tools. Some commonly used risk measurement tools are Value at Risk (VaR), Expected Loss (EL), and Stress Testing. (3) Manage risks: Once risks are identified and measured, Pegadaian Syariah needs to manage risks in an appropriate way. Some ways that can be done are by setting risk limits, monitoring risks regularly, and taking action to reduce risks if unwanted risks occur. (4) Insurance: Islamic Pawnshop can purchase insurance to protect themselves from risks associated with gold pawning activities. Insurance can help reduce risks and financial losses that can arise as a result of these risks. (5) Employee training: Islamic Pawnshop must provide training to employees regarding risk management, so that employees can better identify risks and take appropriate action to manage risks. (6) Risk evaluation: Islamic Pawnshop must regularly evaluate the risks associated with gold pawning activities to ensure that the risk management strategies implemented are still appropriate to the existing risks.

Ninth, protection of gold savings investment products. The mechanism is: (1) Insurance: Gold savings investment products at Pegadaian Syariah are protected by life and accident insurance from leading insurance companies. This insurance will provide protection for customers from the risk of loss or damage to gold stored at Pegadaian Syariah. (2) Musyarakah Contract: Sharia Pegadaian uses a musyarakah contract for gold savings investment products. The musyarakah agreement is a form of collaboration between Pegadaian Syariah and the customer, where the customer provides capital and Pegadaian Syariah provides management and expertise in managing gold. In this case, the customer becomes a joint owner of the gold and receives profits based on the agreement. (3) Security Guarantee: Sharia Pegadaian has a strict security system in managing customers' gold. Gold stored by Pegadaian Syariah will be stored in a safe that has a 24-hour security and monitoring system.

Tenth, restructuring of problematic financing with gold collateral as collateral. The mechanism is: (1) Identifying the problems underlying the problematic financing, which can be done through analysis of financial data and customer risk profiles. (2) Next, evaluate the guarantee provided by the customer as a financing condition, where the gold pawn guarantee must be reassessed so that the value offered can be in line with the actual value of the gold and minimize the risk of default; (3) After identifying problems and evaluating collateral, it is necessary to consider restructuring options that can be carried out, which could be in the form of extending the payment period, reducing the number of installments, or adding other collateral; (4) After determining the appropriate restructuring option, negotiations need to be carried out with the customer to resolve the problematic financing problem. In this case, it is also necessary to pay attention to the customer's ability to pay the new installments offered; (5) After successful negotiations, it is necessary to implement the financing restructuring. Pegadaian Syariah must ensure that customers comply with the agreement and make payments according to what has been agreed; (6) Finally, it is necessary to monitor and evaluate the implementation of the restructuring. This is done to ensure that customers can

fulfill their obligations in accordance with the agreement and minimize the risk of problems in the future.

Eleventh, settlement of defaults in the gold pawn agreement. To resolve a default in a gold pawn agreement at a Islamic Pawnshop, there are several steps that can be taken, including:

- (1) Notifications and warnings to parties who are in default. The party experiencing default must be informed in writing regarding the violation that has been committed, including the consequences that may occur as a result of the violation.
- (2) Negotiations between the two parties. After notification is given, both parties can negotiate to find the best solution to resolve the default.
- (3) Mediation. If negotiations do not produce a satisfactory agreement, the parties involved can try to resolve the dispute through mediation, which is a dispute resolution process involving a neutral and independent third party.
- (4) Arbitration. If mediation is unsuccessful, the parties involved can choose to resolve the dispute through arbitration, which is a dispute resolution process involving one or several arbitrators chosen by both parties.
- (5) Settlement through court. If all efforts to resolve the dispute outside court fail, then the party affected by the default can file a lawsuit with the court to resolve the dispute.

Twelfth, non-real gold purchase transaction from the perspective of akad ba'i al-muqayyad. In the perspective of akad ba'i al-muqayyad in Islamic Pawnshop, the transaction of buying non-real gold is done by using the buying and selling mechanism arranged in the contract agreed by both parties, namely the buyer and the seller. The contract covers conditions that must be met, such as the price, amount, and time of gold purchase. The following are the transaction steps for the purchase of non-real gold at Islamic Pawnshop using the ba'i al-muqayyad contract: (1) The buyer and seller agree to the conditions stipulated in the non-real gold sales contract, including the price, amount, and time of purchase; (2) The buyer provides the required payment for the purchase of non-real gold, which payment can be made by transfer or cash; (3) Sharia pawnbroking then issues a non-real gold certificate as proof of ownership of the gold by the buyer; (4) Buyers can take non-real gold that has been purchased after a gold certificate is issued by a Islamic Pawnshop; and (5) The buyer can resell the non-real gold he has bought back to the Islamic Pawnshop using the same sales contract.

Mapping Literature Review regarding the Influence of Islamic Pawnshop

literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 6 influences caused by the existence of Islamic Pawnshop, namely:

First, community welfare. Islamic Pawnshop can have a positive impact on people's welfare, especially for those who have difficulty meeting their financial needs. Through a financing system based on sharia principles, Pegadaian Syariah provides easy access to financing at affordable costs, so that people can meet their daily living needs and improve their quality of life. Apart from that, Pegadaian Syariah also provides an alternative solution for people who have difficulty accessing financing from conventional financial institutions that apply an interest system. With sharia principles that prioritize justice and mutual benefit, Pegadaian Syariah can help people overcome financial problems more fairly and transparently.

Second, development of MSMEs. Islamic Pawnshop can play an important role in the development of MSMEs, especially in terms of financing working capital and investment. MSMEs often experience problems in accessing financing from conventional financial institutions which require guarantees that are difficult for MSMEs to fulfill. In this case, Pegadaian Syariah can provide an alternative solution by offering financing that is based on sharia principles, such as murabahah, mudharabah and musyarakah financing. With sharia principles that are more flexible and in line with the characteristics of MSMEs, Pegadaian Syariah can help MSMEs develop their businesses and increase their competitiveness in the market.

Third, business capital. Islamic Pawnshop can provide access to business capital financing for business actors who need it. In this case, Islamic Pawnshop can provide loans with collateral for goods handed over by the borrower. Borrowers can use these funds to finance business capital and develop their business. As a financial institution that follows sharia principles, Islamic Pawnshop offer products that do not involve interest or usury, so they are a financing alternative that complies with sharia principles and can be chosen by business actors who respect these principles.

Fourth, sharia financial literacy. Islamic Pawnshop can be a source of information to increase sharia financial literacy. This financial institution can provide education about sharia financial products, as well as the sharia principles that underlie these products. By increasing sharia financial literacy, people can understand sharia financial products and the principles related to their use, so they can choose financial products that suit their needs and adhere to sharia principles. This can also increase public trust in sharia financial products and can encourage the growth of the wider sharia financial industry.

Fifth, fulfilling household economic needs. Islamic Pawnshop provide access for people to borrow money with pawn collateral permitted by sharia, such as gold or jewelry. In this case, Islamic Pawnshop can help meet urgent household economic needs, such as education, health or daily needs. Apart from that, Islamic Pawnshop can also help reduce poverty levels, because they provide access to people who do not have access to capital markets and conventional financial institutions.

Sixth, people's income. Islamic Pawnshop can also contribute to increasing people's income. This is especially true for those who have assets that can be mortgaged, such as jewelry, land, or vehicles. In this case, Islamic Pawnshop provide access to asset owners to obtain funds easily and affordably. Apart from that, Islamic Pawnshop can also help small and medium entrepreneurs (SMEs) in obtaining working capital and increasing their business productivity. Thus, SMEs can expand their businesses and increase income.

Mapping Literature Review around Islamic Pawnshop

Based on a literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 34 findings regarding Islamic Pawnshop, namely: (1) Theory and practice; (2) Pawn law based on Islamic law, KHES, muamalah fiqh; (3) Analysis of determining financing recipients based on 5C/Character, Capacity, Capital, Collateral, Conditions; (4) Imposition of Rahn administration fees; (5) Product marketing strategy; (6) Auction of collateral goods in accordance with Fatwa No. 25/DSN-MUI/2002; (7) OJK Regulation No. 31/POJK.05/2016; (8) Islamic Pawnshop income accounting; (9) Customer Relationship Management/CRM Strategy; (10) Bad credit in granting pawn

credit; (11) Operational risk analysis; (12) Concept, operationalization, prospects, potential, development and development constraints; (13) Determination of Ijarah fees; (14) Implementation of fiduciary agreements and legal protection; (15) Implementation of the determination of compensation/ta'widh; (16) Normativity of Islamic Pawnshop and their practices; (17) Implementation of Maqashid and minimizing social inequality; (18) Management of handling problematic product financing; (19) Fatwa no. 92/DSN-MUI/2014; (20) Application of late fines; (21) Loss or damage to pawned goods; (22) Comparison of profit and operational calculation models with conventional Pawnshop; (23) Use of remaining customer money; (24) Risk management of unredeemed non-gold pledges; (25) Murtahin's Default; (26) Financing risk management; (28) Rahn's financing has a hybrid contract and multi-contract concept; (29) Implementation of the Ijjarah contract; (30) Rahn Tasjily agreement on pawning of movable objects and agricultural land; (31) Two-wheeled ownership financing; (32) Hajj financing; (33) Ar-Rahn financing for micro businesses/ARRUM; and (34) Gold social gathering products.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Determinant Variables of Customer Satisfaction, Profitability Level, Return Rate, Financing Distribution and Human Resource Performance at Islamic Pawnshop

Based on a literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 57 determinant variables of customer interest and satisfaction in choosing to transact at Islamic Pawnshop, namely: (1) Service quality, including: tangibles/physical evidence, reliability, responsiveness/responsiveness, assurance/assurance, empathy; (2) Knowledge; (3) Differentiation; (4) IT- Performance; (5) Organizational culture; (6) Innovation; (7) Operational strategy; (8) Promotion, including: following a friend's invitation, being invited by Islamic Pawnshop employees, through advertisements, brochures; (9) Motivation; (10) Marketing strategy; (11) Income; (12) Education level; (13) Family dependents; (14) Location; (15) Information; (16) Service quality; (17) Digital Application Information System; (18) Sharia compliance, including: operating in accordance with sharia principles, products do not contain usury/interest, avoiding haram business; (19) Appraised value; (20) Loan disbursement procedures; (21) Administrative costs; (22) Reputation; (23) Product innovation; (24) Trust; (25) Religiosity; (26) Brand equity; (27) Confidence; (28) Service fees; (29) Product diversity; (30) Gold price fluctuations; (31) Customer satisfaction; (32) Product use; (33) Risk perception; (34) Convenience; (35) Marketing intelligence; (36) Sharia management; (37) Integrated Marketing Communication/IMC; (38) Consumer attitudes; (39) Subjective norms; (40) Voting decisions; (41) Family; (42) Social and cultural; (43) Pricing; (44) Company image; (45) Period of rental of premises; (46) Security; (47) Responsibility; (48) No indication of bankruptcy; (49) Profit sharing; (50) Professionalism; (51) Technology; (52) Market segmentation; (53) Financial literacy; (54) Benefits; (55) Quality of Multi Payment Online/MPO service; (56) E-Government; and (57) Pegadaian Syariah Digital Service/PSDS.

literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are determinant variables for the level of profitability, namely: (1) Number of estimates; (2) The amount of money borrowed; (3) Covid-19 Pandemic; (4) Products; (5) Sales of precious metals; (6) Gold pawn financing; (7) ARRUM Financing; (8) Gold price; and (9) Money supply.

literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 4 determinant variables on the level of return on financing, namely:

(1) Amount of financing; (2) Business turnover; (3) Inflation; and (4) Business income.

literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 10 determinant variables for financing distribution, namely: (1) Poor population; (2) Profit margin; (3) Inflation; (4) Gold price; (5) Number of customers; (6) Income; (7) Accuracy of Marhun digital scales; (8) Non-Performing Loan/NPL Level; (9) Sharia compliance; and (10) Asset growth.

literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 8 determinant variables of Human Resources performance, namely: (1) Employee performance; (2) Ethical leadership; (3) Organizational commitment; (4) Transactional leadership style; (5) Performance assessment; (6) Capacity Building; (7) Training; and (8) Career development.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- Number of research publications around Islamic Pawnshop during the period 1999 to 2022 are 312 research articles, originating from the indexed national journal Sinta.
- The affiliate/institution that publishes the most research results is the Journal of Islamic Economics and Business, with 27 articles.
- In the mapping visualization using VOSviewer, research developments regarding Islamic Pawnshop are divided into 4 clusters and 115 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 47 topics, cluster 2 consists of 40 topics, cluster 3 consists of 15 topics, and cluster 4 consists of 13 topics. The fewer clusters that are formed, the less scope for research regarding Islamic Pawnshop.
- Based on a literature review, there are 8 The main themes surrounding Islamic Pawnshop are: (1) Implementation; (2) Gold pawn products; (3) Determinant variables of community interest and satisfaction; (4) Determinant variable for profitability level; (5) Variables determining the rate of return; (6) Determinant variables for financing distribution; (7) The impact caused; and (8) Employee Performance.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- the literature review study can be explained in a more complex way.

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